

Newsletter

What is MSCA Ideal4Green?

The IDEAL4GREEN project addresses the urgent challenges of climate change and the global shift towards sustainable energy systems. The focus is on developing and integrating microgrids into electricity networks, which are crucial in managing the variability of renewable resources and achieving decarbonization targets. The project aligns with the EC's commitment to carbon neutrality by 2050 by empowering energy communities and optimizing local supply and demand.

The project proposes a comprehensive doctoral training network aimed at developing skilled engineers with interdisciplinary and inter-sectoral expertise. This network diverges from conventional university-based research, maintaining strong industry links and emphasizing practical implementation.

Building decentralised, distributed and local microgrids for decarbonisation electrification challenge

THE IDEAL4GREEN PROJECT

IDEAL4GREEN consists of 8 beneficiaries and 11 partner organizations, recruiting 15 doctoral candidates to undertake research on microgrids' planning, design, operation, control, and impact assessment. The research encompasses innovative frameworks and methodologies for integrating microgrids and transforming traditional grids into sustainable energy systems. This includes developing advanced control algorithms, cybersecurity, improving mechanisms for microgrid islanding and reconnection, and enhancing the resilience and reliability of interconnected microgrid systems. The project also explores the planning, policy, and economic feasibility of interconnected grids and microgrids. It emphasizes creating complete and integrated microgrid design frameworks, utilizing integrated energy system modelling, and investigating regulatory policies. In terms of training, the DCs will engage in a mix of academic and industrial experiences, including secondments and networking meetings, ensuring their exposure to both theoretical knowledge and practical skills. The training program covers various aspects, such as advanced technical skills, collaborative communication, critical thinking, problem-solving, and adaptability.

WORK PACKAGE OVERVIEW

The IDEAL4GREEN project is divided into six Work Packages, each addressing a key aspect of the project's goals. Each WP is designed to complement the others, creating a cohesive framework for achieving the IDEAL4GREEN objectives. By combining cutting-edge research, strategic planning, and robust training, this project seeks to produce innovative energy solutions while training the next generation of energy experts. Below is a detailed breakdown:

- **WP1:** Project Management
- **WP2:** Technological Integration and Control
- **WP3:** Resilience and Reliability Enhancement
- **WP4:** Planning, Policy, and Economic Feasibility
- **WP5:** Training and Recruitment
- **WP6:** Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

EVENTS

Kick-off Meeting

On January 13, 2025, the IDEAL4GREEN project officially launched with a full-day online meeting, bringing together top academic institutions and industry leaders to set the stage for this groundbreaking initiative.

IDEAL4GREEN, a collaborative effort of 8 academic institutions and 11 industry partners across Europe, aims to pioneer innovative microgrid technologies to meet global decarbonization targets.

Supervisory Board meeting

Our first Supervisory Board meeting was held online on 10th June 2025. The supervisory board, with its mix of academic and industry experts, focuses on the scientific and technological integrity of the project, providing insight to guide the direction of the doctoral network and ensuring that it meets high standards of research. During this meeting, the process of DC selection was formalized.

Ideal4Green DOCTORAL CANDIDATES SELECTION UPDATE

We are pleased to share the latest update on the recruitment process for our Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Doctoral Network – IDEAL4GREEN. The call for applications received an overwhelming response, with 750 applications submitted for 15 doctoral candidate positions. The gender distribution of applicants reflects a growing diversity in research interests:

- 128 female applicants
- 613 male applicants
- 9 non-binary applicants

Applications were received from across the globe, with particularly strong profiles from countries including Iran, India, China, Kenya, Ethiopia, and Egypt, among others. The local supervisory team, including the representatives of the secondment companies, conducted the evaluation, and we are very satisfied with the overall quality of candidates and the resulting selections.

While most positions have been successfully filled, a few have been reopened to ensure the highest-quality match between candidates and research objectives. We anticipate that all doctoral candidates will join their host institutions by November 2025.

Top European academic Partners

Top European Industrial Partners

Funded by the European Union

Ideal4Green

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MSCA Doctoral Networks 2023 IDEAL4GREEN project aimed at pioneering decentralized energy solutions to meet global decarbonization targets through innovative microgrid technologies.

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